

Biomimicry in Architectural Designs

Nkandu, Mwila Isabel and Halil Z. Alibaba. “Biomimicry as an Alternative Approach to Sustainability.” (2018).

This secondary research paper talks about how nature strains all the unwanted or harmful elements to the environment and the different ways that biomimicry could be used. Three methods of mimicking nature are discussed in the paper. The organism level is the imitation of an organism and in this case, the Gherkin Tower is used as an example which is mimicking the Venus Flower Basket Sponge (Fig. 1). Some of the advantages of the design are the easy access to light and air due to the 5-degree rotation between the floors (Nkandu & Alibaba, 2018). The shape of the building also allows “passive cooling, heating, ventilating, and lighting techniques through the double skin façade.” (Nkandu & Alibaba, 2018). Thus, reducing the use of energy, and the resources that would have been used for air ventilation. The second method of mimicking is behavioral mimicking and the example used in the research is The East gate Center in Zimbabwe which takes inspiration from self-cooling termites (Fig. 2). The window ratio and location allow the building to keep a neutral temperature that does not drop at night and does not increase in daylight. The third method is the Eco-system level and this level is a mixture of the behavioral and the organism method, in the third method, the building acts like an organism and produces no waste. The example that presents this method is The Cardboard to Caviar Project in Wakefield UK, Qatar, Jordan, Tunisia, and Cornwall England. In Wakefield, for example, the project started with taking cardboard from restaurants and transforming it into bedding for horses in the stable and then used to construct a wormery composting system. After that, the cardboard is used for a start-up of a Siberian Sturgeon fishery that is sold back to the restaurants. This

program opens our eyes to that a system without waste and how easily it creates opportunities to increase the economic and environmental state of the people. The research proves that biomimicry is a new solution to the puzzle of sustainability, bringing together separate fields of study and work, using interdepartmental knowledge that does not limit people in their methodological frameworks; for the common goal of reducing waste.

This research was useful in helping me understand my topic because I did not know the different forms of imitating an organism or nature and I was able to come up with a design that has a specific purpose. This secondary source revealed the interconnectedness of the environment and the energy that we use in everyday life and how it impacts all the areas around us. This paper was more helpful in the aspect of teaching me about the different ways of imitating nature and providing examples that are still relevant.

Pawlyn, Michael. *Biomimicry in Architecture*. RIBA Publishing, 2020.

This book by Pawlyn discusses how biology could be the solution to human problems and how biomimicry could be the answer to nowadays functional challenges. Pawlyn states that his mission is “to make the world work for a hundred percent of humanity, in the shortest possible time through spontaneous cooperation, without the disadvantage of anyone (Pawlyn, 2020).” By this, he means taking advantage of what the world has to offer to humans and it is way much easier to do biomimicry now because our knowledge of science has increased and developed. Then he discusses the different ways used to address the process of imitating nature or an organism. He compares the terms used to describe the action of imitating nature, and some

of the ones he discussed are biomimicry, biomimetic, and bioinspired. He personally does not prefer using bio-inspired because he feels like it is too broad and it hints at maybe adding new developments while biomimicry is copying. For example, he discusses how the process of a wasp drilling wood could be beneficial for neurosurgeons that handle delicate parts of the human body since wasps use a method that drills without a rotating axle.

This source revealed the history of biomimicry and how it has evolved throughout the years. He states that it is not something that we are only discovering now but it was always developing with us. For example, using spears and making the head of the spear the teeth of an animal or as sharp as a teeth. His main argument was shedding light on the potential that mimicking nature holds for architecture and the development of the human in general. This source was useful in helping me understand the different terminologies that I should use with my design and providing examples that are outside of the architecture department. The source was helpful in its own way but I believe that it was more scientific.

Tavsan, Filiz, and Elif Sonmez. "Biomimicry in Furniture Design." *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 197 (2015): 2285–92.

In this research, biomimicry is used as a way to explore the art, color, and technique that nature adds to designs when we take inspiration from them. This research presents that there is no disadvantage to imitating nature, especially when designing furniture. It is a way of either being more artistic and innovative or if imitating is not possible then you find other ways to be inspired by a specific organism. Which will result in a product that perfectly mimics or one that goes through trial and error and becomes the beginning of a new discovery of technique or

furniture. For example, the research examines the case study of the 44 students that went through the 6-stage biomimicry seminar. In the last stage of the study, the students modified regular white stools taking inspiration from a variety of different microscopics and organisms. For example, peacocks, Luminous Algae, smooth muscle cells, nerve cells and etc. (Fig.3). The paper echoes how biomimicry is new to the field of humanities and design and could be a great potential for ornamentation in interior design.

The source reveals the role of biomimicry as decoration, specifically in terms of furniture and interior design. It provides a different view of biomimicry that is not all about science or for environmental purposes but that it could also be used to beautify the spaces that we spend most of our time in. It was useful in helping me understand my topic in the sense that it challenged me to not only think about sustainability and the function of my work but also to make it appealing to the eye. It was helpful in the sense that it gave me a different perspective of biomimicry that was not mentioned in the other sources I have read. It was also the only one that related to my project idea of furniture because the rest of the sources discussed building designs.

I have neither given nor received unauthorized assistance on this assignment

Hodo Yassin Abubakar

The Gherkin Tower, comparison with the Venus Flower Basket Sponge.

Norman Foster, Ken Shuttleworth.

April 28, 2004. London, United Kingdom

Source: Nkandu, Alibaba. "Biomimicry as an Alternative Approach to Sustainability."

Department of Architecture, Eastern Mediterranean University, Mersin, Northern Cyprus
(2018): 4.

The East gate Center in Zimbabwe, comparison with a termite nest.

Mick Pearce.

1996. Harare, Zimbabwe.

Source: Nkandu, Alibaba. "Biomimicry as an Alternative Approach to Sustainability."

Department of Architecture, Eastern Mediterranean University, Mersin, Northern Cyprus
(2018): 6.

Student Work	Interaction	Description
	Inspired by “Bacillus subtilis” bacteria form. Covered the stool surface with a material of the same shapes	
	Inspired by “Smooth muscle cell” form. Completed the design by using the same gaps on the surface.	
	Inspired by cell form of “Protozoa” bacteria. Tried to reflect this effect by opening similar gaps on stool surface.	
	Inspired by “Nerve Cell”. Applied structures like nerve structure on the stool surface	

Figure 7. Example of Student Work

This is the work of the groups of students.

February 2015. Trabzon, Turkey.

Source: Tavsan, Sonmez. "Biomimicry in Furniture Design." *Karadeniz Technical University Interior Architecture* (2015): 2290.